

Modification to the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 25, 2020

In previous notes, we argued the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution (as well as the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein) may be obtained by a time reversal elastic two particle scattering balance. This approach requires no concept of entropy, counting of states or partition functions. For the MB case, one may write $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ ((1a)) to describe $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((1b)). Taking \ln of both sides of ((1a)) and associating with ((1b)) yields the MB distribution. The scattering approach allows one to visualize a physical mechanism (i.e. elastic scattering) create the equilibrium balance, but it also exposes some possible issues, it seems. First of all, there are cases where $f(e_i)$ is very small i.e. the particle energy is very large. For a gas with numerous particles, it is possible that a high energy particle is created in one place (forward reaction of ((1a))), but that the reverse reaction occurs quite a distance away. Overall, there would be a reaction balance and equilibrium, but locally it seems there would be two large fluctuations at two different places. These fluctuations would disturb local equilibrium which would then need to be restored. Furthermore, it seems a reaction balance has to occur locally in a certain amount of time. In such a time period, low energy particles might scatter once, while high energy particles may scatter more than once. This would change ((1a)) it seems, enhancing $f(e_i)$ for the higher energy particle. As a consequence of ((1a)), it would enhance lower energy $f(e_i)$ as well. Thus, the MB distribution may be changed. E.g. the standard deviation increased. In this note, we try to examine these issues, albeit in a very handwavy manner.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and Fluctuations

The MB distribution may be obtained directly by considering time reversal balance of two body elastic scattering. Thus, one uses ((1a)) and ((1b)) i.e. $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. Taking the \ln of ((1a)) and equating to ((1b)) yields the MB distribution. Similar arguments hold for the Fermi-Dirac and Bose Einstein cases, and even a generalized theory due to Kaniadakis (1), may be expressed in terms of $\ln(k(f(e_i))) = -1/T (e_i-u)$.

The scattering approach does not make use of entropy or partition functions and simply requires that particle numbers (of different e_i) be conserved through elastic reactions which already ensure energy is conserved.

A possible issue with this result, is the lack of a cutoff energy for the distribution. All possible scattering reactions are allowed (as long as energy conservation is not violated). In other words, one may have an extremely high e_i (implying that many other e_i are 0) in equation ((1a)). This would appear as part of a reaction balance, but in fact, it seems it is more likely treated as an extreme fluctuation. Furthermore, even if e_i is more reasonable (not such a high value), $f(e_i)$ may be very low. Thus, the reaction balance ((1a)) might only occur globally in a large spatial region and not locally. Thus, locally, one would again have an off-equilibrium fluctuation. As a result, locally the system should try to restore equilibrium, but the balance reaction implies equilibrium is already maintained. Further issues may also occur if some high energy e_i levels

may react twice in the time that others react once. This should modify ((1a)). We try to examine double scattering in more detail in the next section. The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, however, has been tested experimentally frequently and if the concerns presented here are correct, it is surprising they have not arisen before. It should be noted, however, that in the literature, some concern has been raised over local non-equilibrium situations which may arise, for example in (2). These authors provide a correction for the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for the Ising Model case and argue it brings the equilibrium distribution closer to experimental data.

Multiple Scattering

It seems there are at least two effects present which may alter the MB distribution. First, there is the issue of local nonequilibrium fluctuations i.e. $f(e_i)$ for large e_i , which appear to be part of the equilibrium ((1a)), but locally seem to be extreme fluctuations. These disrupt the local equilibrium, it seems, which then has to be reestablished. Thus, the equilibrium distribution would be a kind of average of the MB case and a nonequilibrium scenario, although the weight of the nonequilibrium scenario should be low because $f(e_i)$ is very low for very high e_i .

The second correction, which we try to examine, in this section is that of multiple scattering. ((1a)), which provides for a reaction balance, seems to imply each reaction occurs once in a little time Δt . Fast particles, however, might scatter more than once in a small Δt time. Thus, it seems that ((1a)) may be altered. We try to crudely estimate this change in a hand-wavy manner. As a first crude approximation, we “arbitrarily” introduce a cutoff energy e_7 . Particles with less energy scatter once, while those with $e \geq e_7$ may scatter twice.

Consider a somewhat large energy, say e_7 that is said to satisfy ((1a)). It is possible that an even higher energy particle, say e_9 has a grazing collision and is converted to e_7 . Since e_9 is moving very quickly, the reaction has to occur quickly, and there is still time for the resulting e_7 to scatter again. Thus, the probability of finding e_7 is not simply the somewhat static $f_{MB}(e_7)$, but is enhanced. If $f_{MB}(e_7)$ is enhanced and it represents a particle on the RHS of ((1a)), then the values of $f(e_1)$ and $f(e_2)$ on the LHS must be enhanced as well. This, it seems, weakens the effect of the increase in $f_{MB}(e_7)$, but overall the MB distribution is changed, not just the tail.

First of all, one needs to choose a starting point for “double scattering”. (One might argue there may be triple scattering etc., but we consider as a first step only double.) One may choose particles say with double the momentum of those in inside the first standard deviation, or four times the kinetic energy. The average energy is $1.5 T$. Here $k=1$. We use e_7 as our cutoff between single and double scattering.

Next, one may consider probabilities associated with grazing collisions. For double scattering, we have argued one wishes a have a high momentum particle scatter into another high momentum state. Alternatively, a high energy particle may collide transferring much of its momentum (a head on collision) and this should also lead to double scattering. It is interesting to note phase space plays no part in the derivation of the MB distribution in the time reversal elastic scattering balance picture. Thus, each reaction $e_i + e_j = e$ has the same probability even though some are grazing and some are direct hits. It seems if one considers conservation of

momentum and energy together (which must be done), then for each reaction e_i, e_j one finds particular cosine values associated with the initial momenta. Thus, phase space does not seem to be a driving force. For example a large momentum particle has more phase space associated with it (a shell with a large radius in momentum) space, but that does not affect a specific reaction in which one may only use one p orientation. The time reversal balance is performed independently for each possible reaction orientation.

Consider a grazing reaction with $2m=1$. For simplicity consider all momenta moving along the x axis.

Then: $e_9 + e_i = e_7 + e_b$ We wish to have e_9 transform into an e_7 moving along the x axis. Momentum conservation yields:

$\sqrt{e_9} + \sqrt{e_i} = \sqrt{e_7} + \sqrt{e_b}$ where $e_b = e_9 + e_i - e_7$ Squaring and using conservation of momentum yields:

$e_i = e_7$. Thus, only one e_i solution is possible in this scenario.

Next, consider the slightly more complicated case of the e_9 momentum vector making an angle of a_1 with the x axis and e_i moving along the x axis. After the reaction, e_7 moves along the x axis (this is the orientation wanted) and e_b moves making an angle a_2 with the x axis. We consider here a grazing reaction. Energy conservation again yields $e_b = e_9 + e_i - e_7$ and $2m=1$

Y momentum $\sqrt{e_9} \sin(a_1) = \sqrt{e_b} \sin(a_2)$

X momentum $\sqrt{e_9} \cos(a_1) + \sqrt{e_i} = \sqrt{e_7} + \sqrt{e_b} \cos(a_2)$

Squaring the y momentum yields $e_9(1 - \cos^2(a_1)) = e_b(1 - \cos^2(a_2))$

Combining leads to:

$$e_9 \cos^2(a_1) + e_i + 2 \sqrt{e_i e_9} \cos(a_1) = e_7 + e_b \cos^2(a_2) + 2 \sqrt{e_7 e_b} \cos(a_2) \quad ((2))$$

For grazing, one would consider e_i and e_b small, thus the $\sqrt{e_i e_9}$ terms might be small corrections. Then $\cos(a_1)$ and $\cos(a_2)$ would need to be very close to 1 for energy conservation to hold. E_9 is very large so $\cos(a_1)$ needs to be extremely close to 1. For y momentum conservation to hold, $\cos(a_2)$ must be less close to 1, but \cos decreases with angle and this would break energy conservation in ((2)). At first, it may seem one may solve for $\cos(a_1)$ in terms of e_9 and e_7 which are given numbers and then obtain a $\cos(a_1)$ for each e_i , but this does not seem to be the case. Thus, it seems that one may again consider the grazing solution of $e_9 + e_7 \rightarrow e_7 + e_9$. The probability for this to happen is $f(e_9)f(e_7)$ it seems. Thus, in time reversal elastic reaction balance, one might modify the e_7 equation:

$$e_2 + e_7 = e_3 + e_4 \quad f(e_2)f(e_7) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad \text{by} \quad f(e_2) f(e_7)[f(e_8)+f(e_9)+...] = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((3))$$

The question becomes how to sum the $f(e_i)$. It seems that one sums in statistical mechanics using momentum. One only has the x axis, so:

$f(e_7)$ becomes $f(e_7) \{1 + \int_{e_7}^{\infty} f(e) dp/\hbar\}$ ((4)) Let $\hbar=1$ Then:

$f(e_7) \int_{e_7}^{\infty} \exp(-e/T) B de / \sqrt{2me}$ where $B = [6.28 / mT]^{1.5}$ ((5))

Here we use $f(e_7)$ as the MB distribution.

This integral may be performed numerically to find the enhancement to e_7 .

For direct head on collisions, a particle with energy e_7 may collide with a stationary particle transferring all of its momentum. This particle, with e_7 , may now take part in a second collision with an e_2 . It seems the probability for this is $f(e_2)f(e_7)f(e_0)$. Thus, for direct scattering, one may have $f(e_7)$ replaced by $f(e_7)(1+f(e_0))$ ((6))

The overall enhancement is ((5)) + ((6)).

If $f(e_7)$ is enhanced by ((5)) + ((6)), then by ((1a)) $f(e_3)$ and $f(e_4)$ (with e_3 and e_4 not large) should also be enhanced. If A is the enhancement of $f(e_7)$, then if e_3 and e_4 are approximately equal, they each receive an enhancement of \sqrt{A} . Thus, the enhancement declines for lower energies.

Thus, it seems double scattering, albeit due to the very handwavy calculation, may change the MB distribution in a measurable way. It seems double scattering may be more of an important factor than the rare extreme energy e_i which would represent a local extreme fluctuation, disrupting equilibrium completely.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue that if one uses time reversal reaction balancing to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann (and also Fermi Dirac and Bose Einstein) distributions, some issues arise. First, a reaction may occur in one spatial region and its time reversed counterpart in a region further away if $f(e_i)$ is very small. Thus, globally there is equilibrium, but locally it appears as if there are two extreme fluctuations. Secondly, for the reaction $e_9 + e_2 = e_7 + e_4$ (with all particles moving in the x direction) (we find $e_2 = e_7$ and $e_4 = e_9$ by momentum conservation), the e_7 produced may take part in the reaction $e_7 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ where e_2 is small and e_3 and e_4 medium. Furthermore, for a head on collision, an e_7 may first hit an e_0 particle and transfer all of its momentum. This new e_7 would then still have time to react again.

Thus, some particles take part in two reactions, possibly enhancing some reactions. We have tried to give a very handwavy calculation of such an enhancement and find that $f(e_7)$ is replaced with:

$f(e_7) \int_{e_7}^{\infty} \exp(-e/T) B \, de / \sqrt{2me}$ where $B = [6.28 / mT]^{1.5} + f(e_7)f(e_0)$

Here we use $f(e_7)$ and $f(e_0)$ as the MB distribution.

This may be calculated numerically. Then, by ((1a)), one must also enhance $f(e_3)$ and $f(e_4)$, but if e_3 and e_4 are close and A is the enhancement of $f(e_7)$, $f(e_3)$ and $f(e_4)$ are enhanced by \sqrt{A} . Again, these arguments are hand-wavy, but are an attempt to measure the change of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution based on a scattering scenario.

References

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